

JAVASCRIPT DASTURLASH TILIDA O'ZGARUVCHI, O'ZGARMAS, OPERATORLAR, FUNKSIYA VA MASSIVLAR HAQIDA

Ismoilov Dilshodbek Sharobiddinovich

Qo'qon davlat redagogika instituti

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JavaScript Kirish

JavaScript garchi browser tamonidan ko'rishni imkoniyati bor bo'lsa ham bu dasturlash tili hisoblanadi. JavaScript dasturlash tilini o'rganishinigizga bir qancha sabablar va qo'layliklar keltirib o'tamiz.

JavaScript dunyodagi eng mashhur dasturlash tillaridan biridir.

JavaScript asosan Web dasturchilar ko'p qo'llaydi.

JavaScript o'rganishga juda oson.

Nima uchun JavaScriptni o'rganish kerak?

Agar siz web dasturchi bo'lib goh backend goh front end dasturchi bo'lishingizdan qat'i nazar JavaScript ga duch kelasiz. JavaScript asosan front end taraflama ko'p qo'llaniladi. JavaScript bilan siz front end da qo'llashingiz mumkin bo'lgan HTML va CSS script tillarini ham boshqara olasiz.

Tez-tez beriladigan savollar

JavaScript-ni qanday olaman?

JavaScript-ni qayerdan yuklab olsam bo'ladi?

JavaScript bepulmi?

Javoblar:

JavaScript ni alohida yuklab olishinigiz zarur bo'lmaydi.

JavaScript allaqochon kompyuteringizda, planshetingizda va smartfoningizdagi brauzeringizda ishlamoqda.

JavaScript bepul!! ;)

JavaScript va Java kontseptsiyada ham, dizaynda ham mutlaqo boshqa tillardir.

JavaScript 1995 yilda Brendan Eich tomonidan ixtiro qilingan va 1997 yilda ECMA standartiga aylandi.

ECMA-262 standartning rasmiy nomidir. ECMAScript - bu tilning rasmiy nomi.

JavaScript O'zgaruvchilar

JavaScript dasturlash tilida o'zgaruvchilarni e'lon qilishning 4 xil usuli bor bo'lib quyidagilar kiradi.

var

let

const

hech narsa ishlatmasdan

O'zgaruvchilar nima?

O'zgaruvchilar - bu ma'lumotlarni saqlash uchun konteynerlar (ma'lumotlar qiymatlarini saqlash). Ushbu misolda, x, yva z, o'zgaruvchilar bo'lib, ular varkalit so'z bilan e'lon qilinadi:

```
var x = 5;
```

```
var y = 6;
```

```
var z = x + y;
```

Ushbu misolni let kalit so'zi bilan e'lon qilishga misol keltiramiz.

```
let x = 5;
let y = 6;
let z = x + y;
Ushbu misolda, x, yva z, e'lon qilinmagan o'zgaruvchilar:
```

```
x = 5;
y = 6;
z = x + y;
```

JavaScript da const ni qachon foydalanish kerak?

Kod yozish jarayonida umumiy qoida bo'lishini hohlasangiz ushbu holatda siz const kalit so'zi bilan o'zgaruvchini e'lon qilsangiz bo'ladi. Bunda o'zgaruvchini o'zgartirib bo'lmaydi. Misol uchun PI ni qiymati o'zgarimas bo'lib uni const bilan e'lon qilishimiz mumkin.

```
const PI = 3.14;
```

JavaScript da var ni qachon ishlatish kerak?

Har doim JavaScript o'zgaruvchilarini var va let yoki const bilan e'lon qiling. var kalit so'zi 1995 yildan 2015 yilgacha barcha JavaScript kodlarida qo'llaniladi. let kalit so'zi 2015 yildan boshlab JavaScript kodlarida qo'llaniladi. Agar siz eski browser ishlatsangiz u holda var kalit so'zidan foydalanishingiz zarur bo'ladi.

JavaScript O'zgarimas

JavaScript dasturlash tilida o'zgarimaslar e'lon qilish uchun const kalit so'zidan foydalaniladi. const kalit so'zi ES6 (2015) dan boshlab ishlatilib kelinmoqda.

O'zgarimasga qayta qiymat yuklab bo'lmaydi.

O'zgaruvchi const kalit so'zi yordamida e'lon qilganimizda unga qayta qiymat yuklab bo'lmaydi.

```
const PI = 3.141592653589793;
```

```
PI = 3.14; // Xatolik yuz beradi
```

```
PI = PI + 10; // Bunda ham xatolik yuz beradi
```

O'zgarimaslarni e'lon qilish.

JavaScript const o'zgaruvchilari e'lon qilinganda ularga qiymat berilishi kerak:

```
const PI = 3.14159265359;
```

XATO!!!

```
const PI;
```

```
PI = 3.14159265359; // xato bunday qilish mumkin emas
```

JavaScript const-dan qachon foydalanish kerak?

const siz umumiy qoida hosil qilish uchun ishlatishingiz mumkin. masalan siz PI ni qiymatini aniq bir songa tengligini bilasiz uni o'zgarimas qilib e'lon qilishingiz mumkin.

```
const PI = 3.14159265359;
```

JavaScript Operatorlar

JavaScript dasturlash tilida ham boshqa dasturlash tillari singari operatorlar mavjud. Bularga quyidagilarni misol keltirishimiz mumkin.

Arifmetik operatorlar

Tayinlash operatorlari

String Operatorlar

Solishtirish operatorlari

Mantiqiy operatorlar

Bitli operatorlar

JavaScript arifmetik operatorlari

Arifmetik operatorlar raqamlar ustida arifmetikani bajarish uchun ishlatiladi:

"+" - Qo'shimcha

"-" - Ayirish

"*" - Ko'paytirish

"**" - Eksponentatsiya (ES2016)

"/" - Bo'lish

"%" - Modul (bo'linish qoldig'i)

"++" - 1 qo'shib borish

"--" - 1 kamaytirib borish

JavaScript Tayinlash operatorlari

Qo'shishni tayinlash operatori (+=) o'zgaruvchiga qiymat qo'shadi.

JavaScript String operatorlari

Operator + qatorlarni qo'shish (birlashtirish) uchun ham ishlatilishi mumkin.

```
let text1 = "Uzbek";
```

```
let text2 = "Developers";
```

```
let text3 = text1 + " " + text2;
```

text3 ning natijasi quyidagicha bo'ladi:

Uzbek Developers

+= operatori qatorlarni qo'shish (birlashtirish) uchun ham ishlatilishi mumkin:

```
let text1 = "Uzbek";
```

```
text1 += "Developers";
```

Uzbek Developers

Satrlarda foydalanilganda + operatori birlashtiruvchi operator deb ataladi.

JavaScript solishtirish operatorlari

"==" - ga teng

"===" - teng qiymat va teng turdagi

"!=" - teng emas

"!==" - qiymat teng emas yoki teng emas

">" - dan katta

"<" - dan kam

">=" - dan katta yoki teng

"<=" - dan kam yoki teng

JavaScript mantiqiy operatorlari

"&&" - mantiqiy va

"||" - mantiqiy yoki

!" - mantiqiy emas

JAVA MASSIV

Massiv bir nechta qiymatlarni o'z ichiga oladigan maxsus o'zgaruvchi hisoblanib JavaScript da massiv o'zgaruvchi yaratish uchun quyidagicha qaraymiz! o'zgarmas massiv keltirilgan.

```
const cars = ["Matiz", "Spark", "Malibu"];
```

Nima uchun massiv?

Dasturlash tilida shunday holga duch kelasiz misol uchun avtomobil ustida misol keltiramiz (Uzavto Motorsga insof bergin deb ishni boshlaymiz 😊) Agar siz bir xil o'zgaruvchi tipiga tegishli o'zgaruvchi yoki o'zgaruvchlarni kiritishingiz uchun har biri uchun alohida o'zgaruvchi nomini topib chiqishingiz zarur bo'ladi. Bu qiyin bo'lmasligi mumkin ammo optimal yo'l emas.

```
let car1 = "matiz";
let car2 = "malibu";
let car3 = "spark";
let car3 = "cobalt" ;
```

Bu kabi keltirilgan misollar bir nechta bo'lishi mumkin ;). Ishimizni osonlashtirish uchun massiv dan foydalanishimiz zarur (Ma'lumot bazasida ham massiv va json dan ko'p foydalanasiz).

```
let cars = ["matiz", "malibu", "spark", "cobalt"] ;
```

Massiv Yaratish

JavaScript da massiv yaratish juda oson hisoblanadi. quyidagicha sintaksisga ega.

```
const array_name = [item1, item2, ...];
```

Massiv elementlarni bir nechta qatorda qamrab olishi mumkin.

```
const cars = [
  "matiz",
  "malibu",
  "cobalt"
];
```

Massiv elementlarni e'lon qilmasdan uni massivni e'lon qilish mumkin bunda siz massiv elementlarini keyin ko'rsatib o'tishingiz mumkin.

```
const cars = [];
cars[0]= "matiz";
cars[1]= "malibu";
cars[2]= "cobalt";
```

Massiv elementlariga murojaat qilish

Massiv elementlari 0 chi indeksidan indekslanadi. Siz massiv massiv elementlariga murojaat qilishingiz uchun uning indeksiga murojaat qilishingiz zarur bo'ladi.

```
const cars = ["matiz", "malibu", "spark", "cobalt"] ;
console.log(cars[1]);
```

malibu

Massiv elementlarini o'zgartirish

Massiv elementlarini o'zgartirish uchun massiv indeksiga murojaat qilib uning yangi qiymatini biriktiramiz.

```
const cars = ["matiz", "malibu", "spark", "cobalt"] ;
cars[0] = "Tayota";
```

Ushbu misolda 0 indeksidagi "matiz" ni "Tayota" ga o'zgartirdi.

Massiv uzunligi

Massiv uzunligi length kalit so'zi biriktirilgan holda topiladi.

```
const cars = ["matiz", "malibu", "spark", "cobalt"] ;
let len = cars.length;
```

4

Massivni birinchi elementiga murojaat qilish.

```
const cars = ["matiz", "malibu", "spark", "cobalt"] ;
```

```
let birinchi_element = cars[0];
```

Yuqorida takidlaganimizdek JavaScript massiv elementlari 0 dan indekslanadi.

Massiv oxirgi elementiga murojaat qilish

```
const cars = ["matiz", "malibu", "spark", "cobalt"] ;
```

```
let oxirgi_element = cars[cars.length - 1];
```

Ushbu misol matematik nazariya qo'llanilgan chunki boshda massiv uzunligi topilib so'ng 0 dan indekslanganligi hisobga olinib undan 1 ni ayirdek.

Eslatma: Matematika bu inson fikrlashini kengaytiradi. Matematiklar va dasturchilarni bir o'xshash tarafi ikkilasi ham oson usulni topishga harakat qiladi va o'z ishidan mamnun bo'ladi.

Massiv elementlarini alohida chiqarish.

```
const cars = ["matiz", "malibu", "spark", "cobalt"] ;
```

```
for (let i = 0; i < cars.length; i++){
```

```
  console.log(cars[i]);
```

```
}
```

```
matiz
```

```
malibu
```

```
spark
```

```
cobalt
```

Massiv elementlarini qo'shish

Massivga yangi element qo'shishning eng oson usuli bu push() funksiyasidan foydalanishdir:

```
const cars = ["matiz", "malibu", "spark", "cobalt"] ;
```

```
cars.push("BMW");
```

Agar siz length kalit so'zi orqali ham qo'shishingiz mumkin. Length massiv elementlarini 1 dan hisoblab massiv indeksiga nisbatan 1 tadan ko'p hisoblandi. cars massivi length 4 chiqadi lekin oxirgi elementi indeksi 4-1 ya'ni 3 chiqadi shunda 4 chi indeks yangi kutilayotgan indeks deb hisobga olib unga qiymat yuklasak massiv elementini o'zgartirmaymiz yangi element qo'shadigan bo'lamiz.

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